

DOI: 10.1002/adma.((please add manuscript number))

Regenerable resistive switching in silicon oxide based nanojunctions**

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Keywords: (Nanodevices, Surface Modification, Electro-Optical Materials, Lithography, Patterning)

Main Text

The development of new ultra-miniaturized devices with memory capabilities is one of the hottest fields in fundamental and applied research because the existing CMOS technology is rapidly approaching its physical limits^[1, 2]. From this perspective, resistive switching^[3] in insulating or semiconducting thin films is receiving great attention due to the versatility and simple architecture of the corresponding devices, which are called “memory resistors” or “memristors”.^[4-6] In the simplest configuration a memristor consists of an insulating or semiconducting thin film sandwiched between two electrodes where the resistive switching occurs after the application of a high electric field.^[4] The thin film can be either inorganic or organic and by using magnetic electrodes, memristors can independently perform both electrical and magnetic resistive switches.^[7] Memristors can operate at high-speed, are amenable to high-density integration, have several non-volatile resistive states with long retention times and a low power consumption.^[8] For all these reasons they are one of the most likely candidates for the post-CMOS technology in nanoscale memory-bit cells.

Although the memristor concept was first proposed theoretically 40 years ago by L. Chua,^[9] a breakthrough towards its application has been achieved only in the last few years, thanks to the skillful combination of thin film and nanofabrication techniques.^[6, 10-12] The key points of the recent technological success of memristors are the use of standard, easily processable and well-studied materials, the simple architecture of the device (e.g. crossbar structures) and the possibility to be fabricated by robust methods compatible with the current technology used in micro- and nano-electronics.^{[13],[14]}

Despite the fact that memristors are quickly approaching the stage of technological application, some major problems remain unsolved, viz. the limited number of program-erase cycles compared to magnetic storage and the cross-talk, which occurs both through the insulating (semiconducting) thin film and via sneak paths through the cross-points.^[15] Even the mechanism of resistive switching remains elusive in most systems.^[16] These problems become more stringent when one passes from the micro- to the nano-scale.

Here we propose an original system based on nano-memristors that offers several crucial technological and scientific breakthroughs compared to conventional devices: i- the possibility to regenerate or repair the junction upon the application of an appropriate voltage cycle; ii- the spatially controlled patterning of the insulating layer, which is fabricated *in-situ*, preventing the problems of cross-talk through the thin film; iii- the usage of removable top electrodes, which allow the unique possibility to expose the two sides of the metal/thin film interface after switching for subsequent investigation.

We demonstrated our approach on a Si/SiO₂/Metal junction where the SiO₂ is fabricated *in-situ* by local oxidation lithography;^[17-19] these materials are commonly used in silicon-based technology^[20]. A scheme of our system is depicted in figure 1 (see detailed description in the experimental section).

Figure 1 here

A metalized stamp is placed in contact with the doped Si surface in a high-humid environment (Fig.1a). By applying a bias voltage (fig. 1b) the sample surface is oxidized, forming an oxide film that perfectly adapts to the stamp features.^[21] The process takes place only underneath the stamp protrusions, moreover, dopants or nanoparticles can be embedded^[22] in the SiO₂ nanostructures during the process.^[23]

The cross-bar-like configuration was obtained by rotating the stamp 90° after the oxidative process (Fig. 1d). Typically, we fabricated oxide lines with a width of 200 nm and a thickness of 10 nm, obtaining an array of nano junctions 200 x 200 x 10 nm³.

Figure 2 here

Figure 2 shows the electrical behavior of the Si/e-SiO₂/Metal junction (where e-SiO₂ means electrochemically fabricated SiO₂). The I-V curve of the device shows a diode-like rectifying behavior (Fig 2a).^[24] After a forming step,^[25] which consists in the application of a large negative bias (usually <-10 V), the I-V curve exhibits a large hysteresis and a sharp resistive switch at a negative bias (Fig. 2b). The device behaves as a bipolar memristor, viz. it is switched ON (i.e. switched in low-resistance state) only by applying a negative bias and it is switched OFF (i.e. switched in high-resistance state) only by applying a positive bias.

The non-volatile character of our devices were tested by measuring the current in they low-resistance state by applying the reading bias. The device was maintained in a short-circuit state between the reading measurements. To elucidate the memory properties of a device, figure 3a shows its resistance measured by using a potential of -0.2 V after each one of a series of -4 V pulses to switch the device ON and +4 V pulses to switch it OFF; we observed a retention time of at least one day.

Figure 3 here

The endurance tests of the memory devices were conducted by repeatedly sweeping the programmed cycles from 1 to -3 V. For optimized devices with a low programming voltage

bias (>-4 V during the write process), we observed an excellent stability over more than 10^5 cycles without any signs of degradation in the devices. The current of the ON-state tends to decrease by $\sim 10\%$ in the first 100 cycles, after which it remains stable over more than 10^5 cycles. The inset of figure 3b demonstrates the stability and the high degree of repeatability of the I-V curve after more than 10^5 cycles.

The endurance is generally less robust (i.e. hysteresis curve becomes unstable) in the samples where the programming bias is <-4 V (about 40 % samples, if prepared under non-optimized conditions, exhibited rapid degradation of the hysteresis curve).

Since the configuration of our memristor is the same used for the fabrication of the e-SiO₂ nanostructures (Fig.1d), the system offers the possibility to be regenerated without the need to disassemble the device.

Figure 4 here

Figure 4 shows an example of a device-regeneration of a device exhibiting fast degradation. The black curve shows the first I-V characteristic after the forming step, while the blue curve shows the I-V characteristic after 1000 cycles. Here the device is regenerated upon the application of a positive voltage higher than +15 V for 500 ms, which establishes again the condition for Si oxidation^[26]. After the application of the regenerative voltage, the device is almost completely regenerated to the original state (Fig. 4, red curve).

Figure 5 here

The proposed configuration offers the unique possibility to investigate the interface after operation by simply removing the top electrode that coincides with the stamp.

Figure 5 show the morphological characterization of the e-SiO₂ stripes before and after applying 10 write/erase cycles (here without rotating the stamp, see the morphology in the cross bar configuration in Fig. S4 in SI). Scanning electron microscopy (Fig.5b) and Atomic force microscopy (Fig. 5d) show the formation of some outgrowths. No traces of metal contaminants were observed in printed structures by Scanning Electron Microscopy

Microanalysis, nor by X-Ray Photon Electron Spectroscopy performed by synchrotron radiation (sensitivity <1%).

Although this work does not aim at investigating the details of the switching mechanism, the peculiar architecture gives access to important information about the switching mechanism. Compared with carrier trapping memory devices and metallic filament based devices, which show no polarity dependence and a crucial dependence on the electrode material respectively, our devices show a polarity dependence but are not influenced by the material of the top metal electrode (we tested Al, Au and Ag, data not shown). Significantly, the hysteresis cycle remained unaltered, even when AgNO₃ or other dopant salts were embedded in the e-SiO₂ during the fabrication process.^[22] In addition, by applying the writing bias in non-optimized or electrically stressed samples, the current increases until it reaches a saturation value after 1000 seconds (~30% of the initial value in the first 2000 ms and a further ~2% within 10³ s, see Fig. S3 in SI).

The observed behavior and the formation of the outgrowths upon a few write/erase cycles, indicates that the resistive switching is caused by an electro-reductive/electromechanical process inducing silicon filament formation, which form after the e-SiO₂ breakdown, as previously observed in the case of poly-Si/SiO_x/poly-Si junction^[27] and carbon nanotube/SiO₂/ carbon nanotube systems.^[28-30] The filaments are destroyed by oxidation when a positive bias is applied. The increase in current observed by applying the writing bias was mainly caused by uncorrelated increases in both ON and OFF-currents and may be explained by a semi-permanent formation of silicon islands inside the e-SiO₂ matrix after repeated application of large driving voltages.

In summary, we demonstrated the concept and application of a new memristor, based on e-SiO₂, which is fabricated *in-situ* with spatial control at the nanoscale. The proposed system exhibits peculiar properties such as the possibility to be regenerated after being stressed or damaged and the possibility to expose the metal and the oxide interfaces by removing the top

electrodes. We demonstrated the feasibility of the method using silicon as a substrate without any process optimization, therefore a significant improvement on the device performance is expected by optimizing the process and by embedding specific dopants and/or nanoparticles in the e-SiO₂.^[22]

The proposed system is compatible with the current (silicon) technology, the resolution of the nanopatterning process can be further downscaled to the spatial resolution of lithography based on local oxidation and extended to many other systems,^[31, 32] including magnetic manganites,^[33, 34] where the magnetic and conducting properties are strictly related to the oxidation state. This will lead to the development of a new generation of memory devices based on resistive switching, where the active, re-generable layer is fabricated *in-situ*.

Experimental

Sample preparation: Si/e-SiO₂/Metal junctions were fabricated using a home-made apparatus as described in ref. 21 in the main text. In order to put the stamp in contact with the substrate, we placed the sample holders at the bottom of the apparatus, so that the stamp was fixed on stamp holder in the top-side and moved downward by a micrometric screw. The substrate is fixed on a rigid sample holder on the bottom side.

The substrate and replica stamps were connected electrically to the voltage source (ELIND Model 3232). Then in order to check the quality of the contact, the resistance between these two electrodes was measured while increasing the applied force. The system was inserted inside the sealed chamber (Tupperware, USA) with feedthroughs for the voltage leads and hygrometer's probe (PCE Model 313-A). The relative humidity (RH) was kept stable by fluxing moist nitrogen. When the RH reached to 90%, the stamp and substrate were put in contact by the downward motion of the micrometric screw. During this process, the resistance between 2 electrodes was monitored while the humidity was kept constant. In this configuration, the silicon substrate / water/ metal stamp system is an electrochemical cell, with the silicon substrate acting as the anode, the pure water layer between silicon and stamp as the electrolyte and the metal stamp as the cathode. Then the bias voltage of 32 V DC with limited current (typically 200 mA) was applied between the electrodes for 30 seconds. The oxidation reaction took place at the anode electrode and at the end of this electrochemical reaction a pattern of parallel oxide lines was formed (Ref. 21 in the main text). The SiO₂ thickness could be varied between 2 and 25 nm depending on the bias voltage, application time and relative humidity^[18, 21]).

Typically, we fabricated oxide lines between 200 nm and 10 nm in width, obtaining cross-junctions with a volume of 200 x 200 x 15 nm³.

Stamps: The elastomeric polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS, Sylgard 184 Dow Corning) stamps were prepared by replica molding. The curing process was carried for 1 hour at 70°C. Once

cured, the replica was peeled off from the master and washed in pure ethanol to remove uncured polymer.

After that, the PDMS replica was coated with a 100 nm thick film of metal by thermo joule evaporation. The stamp motif consists of parallel lines with a periodicity of 1.4 μm , a width at the apex of 200 nm and a depth of 200 nm. In some experiments the coating of commercial blank compact disks was directly used as stamp.

Substrates: The substrates were $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces of Si p- and n- doped, covered with a native silicon oxide layer (Siltronic, type n and p, 0.5 mm thick, orientation [100], resistivity of n type: $\rho = 0.0015 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$ and p type: $10 < \rho < 20 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}$). The substrates were cleaned by: sonication for 2 min. in electronic-grade water (milli-pore quality), 2 min. in acetone (Aldridch chromatography quality) then 2 min. in 2-propanol (Aldridch spectroscopic grade quality).

Scanning Electron Microscopy: The Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were obtained with a ZEISS 1530 SEM equipped with a Schottky emitter and operating at 10 keV. The instrument was equipped with an Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectrometer (EDX) for X-Ray microanalysis, and two different Secondary Electrons (SE) detectors, the InLens (IL) and the Everhart-Thornley detectors (ETD). The IL detector collected a secondary electrons component (the so-called SE1) generated by the primary incident beam in a small region around the beam impinging point, and for this reason it shows an higher sensibility to surface morphology. The ETD collects the complete SE spectrum, the SE1 component, but also the SE generated by the back scattered electrons (BSE) emitted by the specimen (SE2) and the SE generated by the BSE colliding with the chamber of the instrument (SE3). In addition ETD acts also as a BSE detector with a rather low efficiency. Therefore the detected signal shows a reduced sensitivity to the local surface morphology, but a higher sensitivity to the density and/or compositional variations.

Atomic Force Microscopy: All the AFM images were recorded with a standalone AFM (SMENA NT-MDT Moscow) operating in air, in intermittent contact mode at room temperature with a relative humidity 55%. Si cantilever (NT-MDT NSG10, with typical curvature radius of a tip of 10 nm and typical resonant frequency 255 KHz) were used. The topographic images were corrected line-by-line for background trend effects by removal of the second-order polynomial fitting.

Electrical measurements: We used Keithley 2612 SourceMeter for I_{SD} measurement, controlled by a dedicated home-made acquisition software. For electrical testing, the bias was applied to the silicon electrode, while the top metal electrode was grounded. The electrical characteristics were measured on devices with 10^6 cross-points in parallel. No relevant difference in the behavior was observed by measuring our memristor without stamp rotation (thus in configuration as in Fig.1B), except for a reduction of the absolute value of the current (see details in Fig.S1).

In order to tests the quality of our junction we used our set-up on Si/ SiO₂ (native oxide) /Metal junction (see Fig. S2 in SI) which confirms the results that can be found in the literature ^[27]

Acknowledgements

We thank Robert Metzger, Jatinder Yakhmi, Valentin Dediu and Ilaria Bergenti for their help and suggestions. We also thank Francesco Borgatti for X-Ray photon electron spectroscopy measurements. The research leading to these results (MC) has received funding under grant ESF-EURYI-DYMOT.

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))
Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))
Published online: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

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- [20] SiO₂ is normally used as an insulating layer. However, it is known that defective SiO_x thin films (x<2) Ref. 27, in which some structural defects are induced by a locally high

electrical field, up to the stage of breakdown, can exhibit memory effects Ref. 2. Intrinsic resistive switching in SiO₂ was observed in several (non)Metal/SiO₂/(non)Metal systems both using thermal and native oxide Ref. 27,28,29; all these systems have excellent switching speeds and durability.

Despite the poor electric properties of electrochemically-fabricated SiO_x (e-SiO_x) Ref. 27,28 thin films for conventional applications in micro-(nano-) electronics, e-SiO_x has appealing characteristics for memristors. e-SiO_x is more porous than the thermal oxide (this can help metal filament formation), it contains a high density of defects and charges trapped in it Ref.18, and it grows in conformity to the electrodes Ref. 21.

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Figure 1. Scheme of the system. A) A nano-electrochemical cell was formed in an environment rich in water vapor by placing a stamp in contact with a Si surface. B) By applying a positive bias the Si is oxidized, in conformity with the stamp protrusions. C) Parallel nanostripes of electrochemical SiO_x (e-SiO_x) were formed. D) A cross-bar like device is fabricated by rotating the stamp by 90°. The inset shows the detail of the Metal/e-SiO₂/Si junction.

Figure 2. Electrical characterization of e-SiO_x pattern, before and after the forming step. A) I/V curve of Si/SiO₂/Al device fabricated by local oxidation. B) Hysteric I/V curved after the forming step (semi-logarithmic scale). The inset shows the same curve in linear scale.

Figure 3. Memory and endurance characterization. A) Memory properties read by using a potential of -0.2 V after a pulse of -4 V to switch ON the device and +4 V to switch OFF. (B) Endurance tests. Demonstration of I/V cycle reproducibility after $\sim 10^5$ cycles. The inset shows a few cycles in detail.

Figure 4. Device regeneration. Non-optimized device exhibits a small hysteresis (black curve), which rapidly degrades after a few cycles (Blue curve), here after 1000 cycles. The device can easily be restored by applying a +15 V bias, which re-oxidizes the semi-permanent silicon filaments (red curve).

Figure 5. Morphological characterization of e-SiO_x pattern, before and after the resistive switching. A) SEM micrograph of e-SiO₂ stripes as prepared; B) InLens Secondary Electrons SEM micrograph after the application of 10 write/erase cycles without stamp rotation. The inset shows a detail of the same sample region, observed with the Everhart-Thornley detectors (see SI), therefore reducing the contribution of the surface morphology to enhance the presence of the outgrowths. The image shows the clear formation of outgrowth smaller than 7 nm in widths. D) Corresponding AFM image of A. D) Corresponding AFM image of B.

The table of contents entry A nano-memristor, based on SiO₂, where the lifetime problem is resolved by introducing a “regeneration” step.

Keywords (Nanodevices, Surface Modification, Electro-Optical Materials, Lithography, Patterning)

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Title (Regenerable resistive switching in silicon oxide based nanojunctions)

ToC figure

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Effect of cross-bar-like configuration (i.e. stamp rotation) on the I/V curve: The absolute value of the current decreased by about 80%, which corresponds to the effective area loss of the electrodes.

Figure. S1 Current reduction associated to the stamp rotation.

In order to exclude possible artefacts due to the peculiar configuration we used, we tested the behavior of our system on Si/SiO₂ (Native) /Metal. The results match those of similar systems that can be found in literature (ref.[27] in the text).

Figure S2. Electrical characterization of Si/SiO₂/Metal devices fabricated using native SiO₂.

Current evolution upon the application of the writing bias: Upon applying the writing bias, the current increases until it reaches a saturation value after 2000 seconds ($\sim 30\%$ of the initial value in the first 1000 ms and a further $\sim 2\%$ within 10^3 s). Figure S3 shows the current evolution, applying the writing bias (-4 V) for 1000 s.

Figure S3. Current evolution maintaining the memristor at the writing bias (-4 V).

Morphological evolution in cross-bar configuration: Figure S5 shows the AFM morphology of the e-SiO_x surface before and after applying 100 write/erase cycles in cross-bar configuration. In correspondence of the cross-point the local roughness increases from 1.9 nm to 3.1 nm and some outgrowths clearly appear. We identify the outgrowths as evidence for filament formation.

Figure S4. AFM morphology of e-SiO_x surface (A) before and (B) after applying 100 cycles. The image shows a local increase of the roughness due to the Si filament formation. Z scale 0-8 nm.